

Elegy for a Dead World

Developed by: Dejobaan Games and Popcannibal

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Keywords

Creative Writing, Literary Studies, Narrative Exploration, Romanticism, Storytelling

Figure 1. *Elegy for a Dead World* (2014), gameplay screenshot. Image © Dejobaan Games & Popcannibal.

Introduction

Elegy for a Dead World (see Figure 1) is an interactive experience that functions as a guided writing simulator, in which players explore landscapes inspired by Romantic poetry. The game's title alludes to Byron's poem "Darkness," which explores the end of civilization and human frailty in the face of an indifferent universe. The world's visual themes prompt players to construct narratives about the fate of the lost civilizations that once inhabited these spaces.

The game's primary audiences are students, educators, and creative writers. It fits into the category of serious educational games because its design emphasizes literacy and creative expression. This positions the game as a tool for teaching writing that fosters imagination and encourages interpretation while aligning with the broader contemporary discourse in serious games.

The game is an experiment in digital authorship. It provides a framework where players can choose to follow structured prompts or abandon them entirely in favor of free-form composition. This transforms the game into an open-ended literary exercise that bridges interactive media with creative writing.

Facts

Release date:	2014 (Retired in 2024, only available if previously purchased through Humble Bundle as a DRM-free release)
Developer:	Dejobaan Games and Popcannibal
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	20 minutes to an hour
Languages:	The game's user interface (UI) is in English, but players can write in any language.
Environment:	It is recommended to play in a well-lit room. A computer or laptop with either Windows or Linux is required.
Material:	Unfortunately, the game has recently been delisted from Steam. Players will need to have already purchased it via Steam or Humble's Jumbo Bundle 7.
Price:	-

Resonance & Criticism

The game has been praised for its innovative concept, and critics have highlighted its potential to inspire creativity and serve as a tool for writers. Khan (2014) notes that it "presents an experience that is all-inclusive and does not look down on anyone who does not fully comprehend it." They state that "whether it is part of your education or one of your passions, writing and literature is an integral part of anyone's life, and so *Elegy* serves as a welcoming platform for anyone who wants to practice writing and polish their craft." However, some reviewers pointed out limitations, for example, *VentureBeat* observed that the game's non-writing elements are lacking (Henningsen, 2014). The game received an honorable mention for the Nuovo Award at the 2014 Independent Games Festival, recognizing its innovative approach to ludonarrative.

Game Principle & Process

Elegy for a Dead World employs a minimalist side-scrolling mechanic where players traverse spaces at a deliberate pace while encountering environmental cues and prompts designed to inspire writing and storytelling. Prompts range from descriptive world-building exercises to character-driven narratives, and free-form writing lets players bypass prompts and write original stories without constraints. Whether players write in free-form or through prompts, movement is linear, with new prompts or pages appearing as they advance through each world. There are no obstacles, enemies, or puzzles, and progression is dictated solely by the player's engagement with the writing process. Since the game lacks interactive branching choices or systemic consequences, players have significant control over the narrative content

but little influence over the world itself. The landscapes and their associated prompts remain static, meaning the player's primary agency lies in interpretation and storytelling rather than gameplay manipulation.

The game's goal is framed as a creative exercise: to complete writing a narrative inspired by its worlds. The act of writing itself becomes the reward, with players able to review their narratives upon completion. Unlike traditional games with challenge-based progression, *Elegy for a Dead World* promotes intrinsic motivation by emphasizing the personal satisfaction of creative expression. The game's aesthetic and narrative themes are rooted in Romantic literature, particularly the idea of the sublime. The barren landscapes reflect the themes of decay and loss in Byron's *Darkness* and Shelley's *Ozymandias*, and their structure follows Roland Barthes' concept of the "writerly text," which invites open-ended interpretation.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Elegy for a Dead World has significant pedagogical potential. It fosters creative writing skills, narrative construction, and literary analysis in an engaging and interactive format. The game can be integrated into literature, composition, or digital humanities courses, to explore themes of solitude, loss, and civilization through both visual and textual mediums as it provides an opportunity for interdisciplinary study by merging game studies with literary theory, narratology, and historical or philosophical discussions about the Romantic movement's preoccupation with decay, the sublime, and the passage of time (Schultz-Colby & Colby, 2008). The game can be linked to constructivist pedagogy, where learning is self-directed, and knowledge is built through active engagement. It provides a scaffolded environment that encourages learners to experiment with storytelling while offering minimal direct instruction.

The educational goal of *Elegy for a Dead World* is to foster creative writing skills by immersing players in visually evocative environments that serve as inspiration for narrative construction. It promotes learning objectives by fostering creativity, critical thinking, and literary engagement. It encourages players to craft original narratives, enhancing their creative and expressive writing skills (Jones, 2023). By requiring players to analyze visual and textual cues, the game develops critical thinking and interpretative abilities while reinforcing storytelling techniques and literary composition.

The teacher serves as a facilitator, guiding students through the game's creative and analytical aspects. Their role includes introducing the game and its objectives by providing context on its Romantic literary influences and instructing students on how to engage with the writing prompts. Teachers would also encourage analytical discussion by facilitating post-play reflections on narrative choices and thematic elements, helping them refine their storytelling skills through constructive critique. While the game is intuitive and does not require extensive technical training, teachers would benefit from spending one to two hours familiarizing themselves with its writing modes. Additional preparation may be necessary if the game is

incorporated into a structured course module to ensure that assignments and assessments align with learning objectives.

Effectiveness

Although there is no peer-reviewed evidence of the game's effectiveness, experiential observations suggest it offers several strengths in fostering creative writing and literary engagement. The game encourages active participation by requiring players to create narratives rather than passively consuming content, fostering independent thought through multiple interpretations without a singular "correct" outcome. Its structured prompts support learners at different levels, guiding beginners while providing experienced writers the flexibility to engage in free-form storytelling, and it successfully blends digital media with traditional storytelling, demonstrating the potential of video games as tools for literary exploration (Jackson, 2017). However, *Elegy for a Dead World* also presents limitations, particularly its lack of direct feedback mechanisms: it does not offer built-in grammar or style analysis, leaving students reliant on self-review or peer feedback. The game's open-ended nature may also require external structuring, as some students might struggle without clear guidance from an instructor.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

While *Elegy for a Dead World* is generally suitable for educational settings, a few aspects of its content and mechanics could present challenges. The game is designed around open-ended creative writing rather than fact-based accuracy, meaning that any historical or literary references are impressionistic rather than rigorously sourced. However, this does not pose a significant issue unless students mistake its aesthetic inspiration for historical accuracy. A more problematic issue is the game's lack of availability. Since the game can only be accessed by those who previously purchased it, new players are effectively locked out of integrating it into their curricula, which limits the game's potential reach.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl

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